

NEP 2020: Teacher Education and Role of Teacher in Holistic Development

Umesh Chandra

Assistant Professor, Department of Teacher Education,
Ganjdundwara College Ganjdundwara, Kasganj, U.P. (India).
umeshucb@gmail.com

Dr. Surendra Pal Singh

Assistant Professor, Department of Teacher Education
D.S. College, Aligarh, U.P. (India)

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ABSTRACT

The goal of teacher education is to improve teachers' proficiency and competency so they can better meet the demands of their profession and solve its issues. From 1906 to 1956, the teacher preparation curriculum was referred to as teacher training. It prepared teachers for careers as mechanics or technicians. It focused only on skill development and had more constrained aims. Consequently, the perspective and scope of teacher education were somewhat restricted. Teaching techniques, solid pedagogical theory, and professional skills are all included in teacher education. The Union Cabinet has approved the new National Education Policy (NEP), 2020, with the goal of bringing about a number of changes to the Indian educational system at every level, from elementary school to university.

- NEP 2020 aims to position "India as a global knowledge superpower."
 - The Cabinet has decided to rename the Ministry of Education as the Ministry of Human Resource Development.
 - The NEP, which was approved by the Cabinet, is just the third major overhaul of India's educational system since the nation's
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independence.

- The two prior education-related strategies were unveiled in 1968 and 1986.

Holistic development basically means that a child develops intellectually, mentally, physically, emotionally, and socially to get ready for the challenges and hardships of everyday life. Above all, professional sectors of employment demand certain talents for success. Every child is unique. His or her beliefs, attitudes, interests, strengths, and weaknesses are all characteristics that define who they are. The curriculum needs to be able to help every child find their unique place in the world that fits with who they are. The whole growth of a child is crucial to achieving this.

INTRODUCTION

'The best teachers are the ones that change their minds.' – Terry Heick

We have a strong enthusiasm for education, yet the current formal education model that is so prevalent is a flawed system built on outmoded ideas. The problem of education reform and the public conversation surrounding it are not new, despite the volume of writing and discussion that has occurred in the last few years. We have selected the most inspiring and forward-thinking reading on school reform from the previous century for you to peruse now.

Guiding students through learning experiences from the darkness of ignorance to the light of knowledge is one of the most significant tasks performed by educational institutions. The primary institution personnel who play a critical role in enacting this shift are the teachers. The instructor is the most important part of a program, as stated by NCTE (1998) in Quality Concerns in Secondary instructor Education. The teacher is the main individual responsible for executing the educational process at all levels. This illustrates how important it is to provide funding for teacher development in order to secure the future of a nation. It is impossible to overstate the value of qualified educators to the country's educational system. Initial and ongoing teacher education must satisfy the demands and expectations placed on teachers by the National Curriculum Framework of 2005.

ROLE OF TEACHER IN EDUCATION

Although they play a critical role in education, teachers play an even more important role in the lives of the students they teach. The ability to instruct students and make a positive impression on them defines a teacher. In general, a teacher's duties in the classroom go beyond just imparting knowledge. Today's educators must take on a variety of tasks in addition to being mentors, external parents, counselors, role models, and so on.

Teachers play a variety of roles in the classroom, including

Sharing Knowledge

First and foremost, teaching is the means by which knowledge is transmitted, and teaching is the primary function of a teacher. Making ensuring that the students understand the content being taught and following a predetermined curriculum are typical aspects of teaching. Since it may be difficult to have any other form of influence on the student if the instructor is unable to fulfill the fundamental obligation of transferring knowledge, all other responsibilities of a teacher flow from this one.

Role Modeling

Although they may not consider themselves to be such, teachers are role models for their students. Because of the length of time they spend with students each day or week, teachers can have an effect on them to some degree. The instructor must now determine whether or not this influence is beneficial. It is about helping a youngster develop their character, not just following a curriculum. Teachers help pupils build their character in addition to teaching them knowledge.

An External Parent

There are more duties involved in teaching than just following a prescribed curriculum and work plan. Teachers unknowingly adopt the role of an external parent since they spend so much time with their students. Teachers can guide students in the right direction by serving as mentors. In this role, the teacher can encourage pupils to realize their full potential and act as a mentor and source of inspiration.

Final thoughts

Within the classroom and in society, the role of the teacher, and in the wider world has changed from the past. With time, educators received guidelines on how to teach the curriculum in addition to a prescribed curriculum to adhere to. The function of the teacher in today's environment has expanded beyond instruction. Teaching pupils how to use and apply knowledge in their daily lives is one of their present obligations, mentoring, and counselling pupils. Educators are currently searching for methods to influence pupils at an entirely new level and even motivate them to be and do more.

Teachers are committed professionals who leave a lasting impression on their pupils. You can use your abilities and enthusiasm as a leader in the education sector by becoming a teacher. This is a fulfilling career to consider if you wish to positively impact the lives of young people. Presenting captivating classes will test your creativity, tolerance, and communication abilities every day. Your commitment to helping students develop their unique skills and intelligence as a mentor and role model will inspire students.

TEACHER EDUCATION

Teacher education is defined by the National Council for Teacher Education as a program of instruction, research, and preparation for teachers at the pre-primary to higher education levels.

The present paradigm divides pre-service and in-service teacher education into two areas. Pre-service education is the collective term for all of the training and educational stages that an educator completes prior to starting their paid career in a school. The education and training a teacher receives after starting his job is known as in-service training. Teacher education refers to the procedures and guidelines designed to provide aspiring educators with the knowledge, perspectives, conduct, and skills necessary to fulfill their responsibilities in the classroom, school, and community at large.

The goal of teacher education is to improve teachers' proficiency and competency so they can better meet the demands of their profession and solve its issues.

AIMS OF TEACHER EDUCATION

The aims of teacher education would therefore be to,

- Providing chances to visit, engage, and establish connections with students.
- Give them the chance to learn on their own, reflect, absorb, and articulate new concepts. Help them improve their capacity for self-directed learning as well as their critical thinking, thinking, and group-working skills.
- Give them the chance to learn about themselves and others, including their thoughts, feelings, and beliefs; help them to become more adept at self-analysis, self-evaluation, flexibility, adaptability, creativity, and invention.
- Give students the chance to learn more, Develop critical thinking skills by analyzing disciplinary material and social reality, making connections between the subject matter and the greater social context, and.
- Provide them with the opportunity to refine their professional pedagogy, documentation, analysis, drama, craft, storytelling, and observational skills.

Teacher Education must include components that would allow student instructors to fulfill such aspirations.

- Taking care of kids and enjoying spending time with them.
- Recognize children in their social, cultural, and political environments.
- See learning as an attempt to make sense of life through one's own experiences.
- Understand the processes involved in learning, how to establish environments that are supportive of learning, and how students differ in the kinds, speeds, and styles of learning they like.
- Think of knowledge creation as a continuous, introspective learning process.
- Keep an open mind and never stop learning.
- Consider learning as the process of deriving meaning from one's own experiences, and consider knowledge creation as an ongoing, reflective learning process.
- Instead of viewing knowledge as an external fact found in textbooks, view it as something that is produced in the shared environments of teaching, learning, and human experience.
- Take responsibility for society and strive towards creating a better world.
- Acknowledge the efficacy of work and practical experience as pedagogical instruments, both in and outside the classroom.
- Examine the texts, policies consequences & curriculum structure.
- Possess solid background knowledge and rudimentary linguistic skills.

NEP 2020

In July 2020, the Union cabinet approved the New Education Policy (NEP), which aims to provide universal education from pre-school through secondary level. NEP-2020, an inclusive framework that focuses on education from elementary school to higher education nationwide, will replace the National Policy on Education (1986). Since assisting children is the primary objective of any educational system, NEP-2020 establishes an aim of achieving a 100% Gross Enrolment Ratio (GER) in schooling by 2030. This is because it is believed that no kid should be denied the chance to learn and succeed due to circumstances surrounding their birth or background.

Key Points

School Education

- All preschoolers through secondary school graduates will get a 100% Gross Enrolment Ratio (GER) education by 2030.
- The goal is to employ an open education system to help 2 crore youth who are not in school reintegrate into society.

- The existing 10+2 system will be replaced with a new 5+3+3+4 curricular structure, which corresponds to ages 3-8, 8-11, 11-14, and 14-18 years.
- The age group of 3-6 years, which is widely recognized as a crucial stage in a child's mental development, will now be incorporated in the school curriculum.
- Moreover, it will include three years of Anganwadi/preschool education out of the twelve years of instruction.
- All pupils should be allowed to retake the board exams for classes 10 and 12, which should be simplified to emphasize essential skills rather than fact memorization.
- The way both public and private schools are governed is about to change soon, since there will be a new accreditation system and independent regulatory authority.
- There is no tight distinction in schools between academic, extracurricular, and occupational domains; instead, the focus is on Fundamental Literacy and Numeracy.
- Starting from Class 6, Vocational Education will include internships.
- Providing up to at least Grade 5 instruction in mother tongue or regional language. No student will have to speak any language.
- Transforming evaluation by employing a 360-degree holistic progress card and monitoring student advancement to fulfill learning objective.
- The National Council of Teacher Education (NCTE) and the National Council of Educational Research and Training (NCERT) will work together to create the National Curriculum Framework for Teacher Education (NCFTE) 2021, which will be updated and complete,
- By 2030, the minimum degree required to teach will be a four-year integrated B.Ed.

Higher Education

- The percentage of students enrolling in higher education is expected to reach 50% by 2035. Furthermore, plans call for the addition of 3.5 million places in higher education.
- The Gross Enrolment Ratio (GER) for the higher education sector is now 26.3%.
- During this period, students can complete a three- or four-year holistic undergraduate degree that offers a flexible curriculum; many exit options, and the required certification.
- M.Phil. classes will be discontinued, and all undergraduate, graduate, and doctoral courses will now be multidisciplinary.
- An Academic Bank of Credits will be established in order to facilitate credit transfers.

- Comparable to IITs and IIMs, Multidisciplinary Education and Research Universities (MERUs) are to be built as national models of the best multidisciplinary education that satisfies worldwide criteria.
- It is anticipated that the National Research Foundation will become the leading entity in fostering a strong research culture and extending research capacities in higher education.
- With the exception of legal and medical education, the Higher Education Commission of India (HECI) would serve as a single, comprehensive body for postsecondary education. Both public and private higher education institutions will be subject to the same rules, accrediting specifications, and academic standards. HECI will also have four distinct verticals, which are as follows:
 1. National Higher Education Regulatory Council (NHERC) for legislation,
 2. General Education Council (GEC) for creating standards.
 3. Higher Education Grants Council (HEGC) for grants,
 4. National Accreditation Council (NAC) for recognition.
- Within the next fifteen years, college affiliation will be phased out and replaced with a staged process that would provide colleges graded autonomy.

NEP 2020: TEACHER EMPOWERMENT

Let's examine more closely at what the National Education Policy 2020 has in store for educators as Teacher's Day draws near in order to help them overcome their current unfulfilling positions, widespread abuse, and demotivating working conditions. The NEP 2020 acknowledges the existence of demoralized and unenthusiastic Indian teachers and proposes a thorough overhaul of the teaching profession to create a robust merit-based system of tenure, compensation, and progression that honors and commends outstanding teachers.

While an empowered teacher is capable of doing great things, the reality is quite different. The 2012 Justice J. S. Verma Committee Report states that over 370 million pupils are at risk due to a deficient teacher education system. The findings of inspections conducted on private Teacher Education Institutes (TEI) showed that their infrastructure was inadequate and their passing percentage was just 99%. Research revealed that teachers failed the Central Teacher Eligibility Test (C-TET), a post-qualification competency test, on average 85% of the time. Post-employment concerns and issues include absenteeism, obsolete teaching knowledge and abilities, a lack of professionalism and commitment, and exploitative employment conditions marked by insecurity and low pay.

Pre-Service Teacher Education

The NEP 2020 guidelines for teacher education and training will serve as the foundation for the development of the National Curriculum Framework for Teacher Education, or NCFTE 2021. For teachers working in academic, vocational, and special education streams, this framework will act as a roadmap for all pre-service and in-service teacher education.

The minimum degree requirement for teachers is a four-year integrated bachelor's degree in education (B.Ed.), which is intended to be both a specialized topic and a multidisciplinary, integrated dual major. For admission to this degree, the National Testing Agency (NTA) will conduct the necessary academic and aptitude tests.

All interdisciplinary universities must establish an education department and collaborate with other departments to conduct B.Ed. programs, including psychology, philosophy, sociology, neuroscience, languages, art, music, history, literature, physical education, science, and mathematics. In addition, they want to carry out cutting edge research in multiple educational domains to raise the standard of their B.Ed. program.

The B.Ed. degree will cover a wide range of knowledge topics and methodologies, along with substantial practicum training. The curriculum will also include learner-centered and collaborative learning, the use of educational technology, educating students with specific needs or interests, multilevel instruction and assessment, and effective methodology for teaching basic literacy and numeracy.

Shorter post-B.Ed. certification courses will also be available to teachers who wish to progress in their careers and go from foundational, preparatory, intermediate, and secondary stages to more specialized fields of teaching or leadership and management responsibilities within the educational system.

It is truly possible to increase the respectability and acceptance of the teaching profession if all new Ph.D. applicants are required to complete credit-based courses in teaching, education, pedagogy, and writing related to their chosen Ph.D. subject during their doctoral training period. These courses should include real teaching experience gained through teaching assistantships.

HOLISTIC DEVELOPMENT

The only way to advance humanity is via holistic education, which transforms society and touches people's souls. In addition to academic standing, most firms and organizations also consider a candidate's overall development when employing new staff members. For this reason, it is essential to

the general development of students in colleges and universities. The days of parents being with their child all day have long since passed. Because of the changes in education methods and the progress made in technology, parents are now interested in making sure their kids are involved in almost every facet of learning. Holistic development has become increasingly important in parenting.

A youngster learns new abilities through exposure to a variety of sports and activities from a young age. This has also had a significant impact on how students are taught in schools, changing it entirely. Since the advent of contemporary technologies and educational methodologies, a child's complete and holistic development has become imperative in preschool. For similar reasons, the importance of students' whole development in elementary and secondary schools has increased.

The five skills for Holistic Development

Cognitive

Strong cognitive abilities enable us to learn how to handle challenging problems in our daily lives, whether they pertain to circumstances at work, school, or in our personal lives. Cognitive skills include things like working memory, problem solving, focus, and flexibility in thought. Acquiring the ability to take on challenging assignments and developing efficient methods to find answers.

Creative

Strong creative abilities enable us to devise original solutions for issues that the world of the future may encounter. Our ability to be creative fosters our receptivity to new experiences and aids in the meaningful transformation of ideas. Developing ideas, expressing them, and making them a reality, accepting uncertainty, investigating options, assessing concepts, and determining the optimal course of action are a few examples of creative abilities.

Physical

Strong physical abilities allow us to exercise both our bodies and minds in order to preserve wellbeing and lead successful lives. Being physically active, mastering sensory-motor abilities to comprehend movement and space, acquiring spatial awareness, and maintaining an active and healthy body is a few examples of physical talents.

Social

Strong social skills enable us to be effective communicators and collaborators. Being socially adept also enables us to maintain positive bonds with our loved ones and friends. Social skills include things like perspective-taking, communication, and teamwork. Developing empathy, negotiating rules, and exchanging ideas.

Emotional

Strong emotional intelligence helps us deal with life's obstacles and form meaningful relationships with our loved ones. Emotional intelligence examples include: Gaining self-awareness, controlling urges, maintaining motivation and self-assurance in the face of adversity, and expressing one's emotions.

ROLE OF TEACHER IN HOLISTIC DEVELOPMENT

One of the largest school networks in the world is located in India. In terms of enrolment and the number of institutions, the system has grown significantly throughout the last fifty years. According to some, the Indian educational system changed from being an exclusive system to a accumulation. For example, there are currently over 600,000 primary schools, compared to only 200,000 in 1950. The network has more than a million schools if one were to add the upper elementary and secondary schools and the numerous alternative schools that have emerged in present time.

The significance of education in learning environments has always grown since independence, and as a result of systemic expansion, the job of the school teacher has also changed significantly. A significant outcome of the school system's expansion, marked by steadily rising enrolment and mass character development, has been the escalation of school administration complexity. The job of a teacher has become increasingly difficult due to the shifting pace of technological advancement, such as ICT and the knowledge revolution. It is imperative that they take on the new tasks and responsibilities associated with ICT and to increase learners' access to it in non-formal and informal learning environments.

The approach requires head teachers and instructors to have new knowledge and abilities. Additionally, it necessitates increased capacity at the school level to address the growing diversity of students and aspiring teachers. The function of the school teacher is now even more crucial than it was before due to changes in the system's characteristics. Has the nation's primary education provider, the State, adjusted to the new reality? Has the teacher's power increased? Has the teacher had enough training to prepare them for the new challenges? What is the current state of affairs regarding the status, responsibilities, and roles of head teachers and teachers in India? And how can we overcome this obstacle? These are a few challenges that require attention, particularly in light of the nation's transition to a knowledge-based economy and how crucial a top-notch education is to such procedure.

HOLISTIC DEVELOPMENT: IMPLICATIONS FOR THE TEACHER

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For both students and teachers, holistic development is a fresh start that will need both to mature and critically assess deeply held values and beliefs. This could be upsetting for the instructor because they are stepping outside of their comfort zone of subject matter expertise and into uncharted territory for themselves. The instructor no longer relies on subject-matter expertise; instead, they help pupils develop and examine their own beliefs and prejudices, critical thinking and behavior, and the ability to confront viewpoints that are unfamiliar to them without making a clear distinction between good and evil. This is uncharted ground. A lot of the time, this is a collaborative voyage of discovery between the teacher and the student, with the teacher contributing their larger life experience to the learning process.

Teachers are challenged by holistic development to reconsider how they approach the cognitive and emotive development of their students and to critically evaluate their own teaching methods. The working dynamic between the teacher and the student shifts to one that is more egalitarian, dynamic, and inclusive. In order to meet students' developmental needs, active, planned interventions will become the ideal instructional strategy. Facilitation, mentorship, and guidance abilities of the teacher largely contribute to fostering learning & comprehension on both social and intellectual levels. For instance, the goal is for students to comprehend the value of relationships, the various perspectives on information and how it should be evaluated, the significance of life skills, and how their actions affect those around them.

Teachers must also assess their school's learning culture to ensure that it supports the development of an inclusive learning community that fosters an individual's creative and curious engagement with the outside world. The goal therefore becomes the growth of healthy, inquisitive people who are self-motivated, self-assured learners who can acquire the knowledge they need and use it in any new situation.

CONCLUSION

Students of today require more in the classroom than just academic teaching. The true meaning of education is an educational system that fosters resilience and teamwork in addition to teaching students how to establish healthy, productive relationships and understand themselves and their emotions and mental stress. A system such as this raises the spirits of students, enabling them to reach greater heights in their jobs and evolve into respectable members of society who further the growth and development of their nation.

Therefore, it is crucial that children' holistic development begin as soon as they start attending school. Teachers and school officials need to make sure that a variety of extracurricular activities are

woven into the curriculum to ensure the overall development of children. Career counselors can provide advice to school administrators and instructors because they are aware of the skills necessary for success in the profession in the future.

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